

1 **Designing national policy for sustainable real world liquid biopsy implementation in Serbia**

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65 **Abbreviations:**

- 66 ASCO/CAP - American Society of Clinical Oncology/College of American Pathologists
- 67 CRC – Colorectal cancer
- 68 EACR - European Association for Cancer Research
- 69 ELBS – European Liquid Biopsy Society
- 70 ESMO – European Society for Medical Oncology
- 71 HMs – Hematological malignancies
- 72 HSCT - Hematopoietic stem cell transplant
- 73 ISLB – International Society of Liquid Biopsy
- 74 ISO - International Organization for Standardization
- 75 LB – Liquid biopsy
- 76 LC – Lung cancer
- 77 MRD – Measurable residual disease
- 78 NGS - Next-generation sequencing
- 79 NSCLC – Non-small cell lung cancer
- 80 OCEBM LoE - Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine Levels of Evidence
- 81 OSCC – Oral squamous cell carcinoma
- 82 PCR - Polymerase chain reaction
- 83 PE – Pleural effusion
- 84 SDIR – Serbian Association for Cancer Research (ser. Srpsko društvo istraživača raka)
- 85 UMOS – Serbian Society for Medical Oncology (ser. Udruženje medikalnih onkologa Srbije)

86 **Abstract**

87 Serbia has been among the highest-ranking European countries in terms of both the incidence
88 and mortality of malignant diseases for many years, due to a combination of various factors - late
89 disease detection, logistical obstacles in preventive and screening programs, high smoking rates,
90 rising air pollution, diet rich in processed food and sedentary lifestyle, among others. Liquid biopsy
91 (LB) was introduced into routine clinical practice in Serbia in 2016, but widening its
92 implementation has proven challenging. In 2025, a national effort spearheaded by the ESMO-
93 affiliated Association of Medical Oncologists of Serbia (UMOS) and the EACR-affiliated Serbian
94 Association for Cancer Research (SDIR) was initiated to design a sustainable strategy for clinically
95 significant LB implementation. The first inter-society Working Group dedicated to LB
96 implementation encompassed physicians and researchers from 15 institutions in Serbia including
97 the business sector as observers. The aim was to develop a clear national strategy for the clinical
98 implementation of LB in oncology in Serbia. A consensus decision was reached during expert
99 discussions with an initial focus on lung and colorectal cancer as depicted in this Policy Paper.

100 **1. Introduction**

101 The Republic of Serbia is located on the Balkan peninsula in Central and Southeastern Europe
102 and has an estimated population of 6 647 003 comprising 51.4% women (3 415 025) and 48.6%
103 men (3 231 978), according to the 2022 Census of Population, Households and Dwellings and data
104 on natural population changes and internal migration from the Statistics Office of the Republic of
105 Serbia¹. Serbia is classified as an upper-middle income country by the World Bank income level,
106 with a health expenditure of 10.01 % of GDP (2021)². The Ministry of Health oversees the
107 organization, regulation and overall governance of the healthcare system. Mandatory public health
108 insurance is financed through the state budget from tax revenues (Beveridge model), with an
109 estimated population coverage of 99%³. The Republic Fund of Health Insurance, as the principal
110 national purchaser of health services, is responsible for the regulation and approval of new
111 procedures and treatments, with particular regard to health economics parameters, especially
112 important in countries with limited healthcare resources.

113 Life expectancy at birth (72.8 [72.8 - 72.9] years in 2021) is below the WHO European Region
114 average (76.3 [76.2 - 76.5] years in 2021) and the probability of dying from non-communicable
115 diseases including cancer between age 30-70 remains comparatively high for Europe (21.4%
116 [15.9% - 26.7%]). However, the number of additional people expected to experience better health,
117 and wellbeing was projected to be 0.9m (0.4m – 1.3m) by 2025 compared to 2018 [1], reflecting
118 ongoing efforts for prevention, earlier detection and better treatment of malignant diseases. Serbia
119 is among the highest-ranking European countries in terms of both the incidence and mortality of
120 malignant diseases, due to a combination of various factors - late disease detection, logistical
121 obstacles and low uptake of preventive and screening programs, high smoking rates, rising air
122 pollution, diet rich in processed food and sedentary lifestyle, among others. According to the most
123 recent official data from the national Public Health Institute “Dr Milan Jovanović Batut” from
124 2024 [2] around 41,472 new cancer cases were registered in 2024 (21,793 in males and 19679 in
125 females), with 20,314 cancer death cases (10,967 in males and 9347 in females). The most
126 prevalent cancer sites in males were lung and bronchus (19.5 %), colon and rectum (15.0 %) and
127 prostate (12.4 %) and in females breast (23.1 %), lung and bronchus (10.7 %), colon and rectum

¹ <https://www.stat.gov.rs/en-us/vesti/20230428-konacnirezpopisa/?a=0&s=1904>

² <https://data.who.int/countries/688>

³ <https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/publications/i/health-systems-in-action-serbia-2024>

128 (10.6 %). Leading cancer death sites in males were lung and bronchus (27.3 %), colon and rectum
 129 (14.3 %) and prostate (9.7 %) while lung and bronchus (19.7 %), breast (18.2 %) and colon and
 130 rectum (10.4 %) were the leading mortality sites in females (Fig1).

131
 132 **Figure 1. Number of new cases and deaths (percentage of total cancer cases) in a) males and**
 133 **b) females in 2024.** Data derived from the Serbian Cancer Registry of the Institute of Public Health
 134 of Serbia “Dr Milan Jovanović Batut” [2].

135
 136 Percentage distribution of new cancer cases and death from cancer in all cancer sites by age
 137 group and by sex in Serbia in 2024 is presented in Figure 2. The burden of incidence and mortality
 138 is present across the working population groups, with the risk of dying from cancer before the age
 139 of 75 years (cum. risk %) of 14.1 in both sexes⁴.

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⁴ <https://gco.iarc.who.int/media/globocan/factsheets/populations/688-serbia-fact-sheet.pdf>

141
 142 **Figure 2.** Percentage distribution of a) new cancer cases and b) deaths from cancer in all cancer
 143 sites by age group and by sex in Serbia in 2024. Data derived from the Serbian Cancer Registry of
 144 the Institute of Public Health of Serbia “Dr Milan Jovanović Batut” [2].

145
 146 Lung cancer (LC) has remained the number one cancer mortality cause in both sexes in Serbia
 147 for many years, highlighting the need for better prevention, screening, early detection and
 148 treatment strategies. Liquid biopsy (LB) was introduced into routine clinical practice in Serbia in
 149 the setting of lung cancer, but widening its implementation has proven challenging. In 2022, a
 150 national analysis of technical, personnel and organizational capacities for implementation of
 151 genomic analyses in Serbia "Genomic Ecosystem of Serbia – Situation Analysis"⁵ was published
 152 as the result of the cooperation of the Center for the Fourth Industrial Revolution of the Ministry
 153 of Health and Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Government
 154 of the Republic of Serbia with healthcare institutions and research organizations. It was found that
 155 13 institutions in Serbia had access to next generation sequencing systems (Illumina, BGI, Oxford
 156 NanoPore Technologies, ThermoFisher Scientific, PacBio) used in diagnostics and research,
 157 enabling future application in LB-based settings needed for designing a nation-wide effort.

158 In 2025, a national effort spearheaded by the ESMO-affiliated Association of Medical
 159 Oncologists of Serbia (UMOS) and the EACR-affiliated Serbian Association for Cancer Research
 160 (SDIR) was initiated to design a sustainable strategy for clinically significant LB implementation.

⁵ <http://c4ir.rs/wpcontent/uploads/2024/02/Genomski-ekosistem-SRB-CIR-1.pdf>

161 The first inter-society Working Group dedicated to LB implementation encompassed physicians
162 and researchers from 15 relevant institutions in Serbia, including the business sector as observers.
163 Joint agenda was established to address LB implementation issues imposed as a result of the
164 continuous advancement of cancer research and clinical oncology, and to address the technological
165 solutions that have not yet been incorporated into the corpus of recommendations for national
166 clinical practice. The aim of the WG is to develop a clear national strategy for the clinical
167 implementation of LB in oncology in Serbia. Two expert meetings, exploring the government-
168 reimbursed LB application in clinical practice, were organized in 2025⁶. These meetings involved
169 mapping the current status and planning future steps in order to review all relevant aspects related
170 to methodological approaches, data processing and sharing, regional specificities as well as the
171 strategic development of this area in accordance with national guidelines. Discussion led by
172 experts reached a consensus decision based on the recommendations of the Oxford Centre for
173 Evidence-Based Medicine (OCEBM) followed by a vote on future recommendations using
174 OCEBM levels of evidence (LoE) starting with an initial focus on LC and colorectal cancer (CRC)
175 as depicted in this first national Policy Paper on LB in Serbia.

176 **2. Clinical practice**

177 **2.1 Lung cancer**

178 In lung cancer, obtaining adequate tissue samples can often be challenging due to difficult
179 anatomical locations of the tumor or poor performance status of many patients, which is a
180 consequence of the cancer itself or comorbidities. Also, repeat biopsies at progression of disease
181 are often not feasible for the same reasons. This is where liquid biopsy has proven to be an
182 important and practical alternative, since it is minimally invasive and can be repeated over time,
183 for as many times as needed. It is routinely used to detect emerging resistance mutations during
184 targeted treatment of NSCLC with actionable mutations but can also be used to monitor response
185 to therapy [3]. Emerging roles of ctDNA monitoring are in testing for residual disease and early
186 detection of disease progression, as it has been shown that rising ctDNA levels often precede
187 radiological progression by a few months [4].

188 Routine ctDNA testing in lung cancer is currently applied in Serbia only for the detection
189 of the resistance T790M mutation during treatment with first- or second-generation EGFR

⁶ <https://english.sdir.ac.rs/first-umos-sdir-colloquium-liquid-biopsy-in-oncology-today/>

190 tyrosine-kinase inhibitors (TKIs). It can also be used for detecting actionable *EGFR* mutations at
191 diagnosis, if insufficient tissue is available. This testing is performed at two institutions only, the
192 Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS) in Belgrade and the Institute for Pulmonary
193 Diseases of Vojvodina (IPBV) in Novi Sad. Testing is done using qPCR and dPCR.

194 At IORS, ctDNA testing was introduced in 2016. So far 513 samples have been tested, with
195 T790M detection rate of 36.6%. In many patients, tests were repeated more than once over the
196 course of their disease (up to 9 times in one patient), which shows one of the main advantages of
197 ctDNA testing, that it can be repeated over time, therefore enhancing the possibility of T790M
198 detection. Also, in 388 patients, testing was done at diagnosis in cases of insufficient tissue, with
199 36 activating mutations detected (9.2%), and 2 exon 20 insertions. Initially, testing was done using
200 qPCR, with a detection rate of 25.2%. Since 2023, dPCR has been used, which yielded a detection
201 rate of 60.8%, showing its superior sensitivity. At IPBV, ctDNA testing also started in 2016. 159
202 samples have been tested so far, with T790M detection rate of 31%. Again, 42 were repeat tests,
203 which yielded another 4 positive T790M tests. This test was also used at diagnosis to detect EGFR
204 mutations in 184 patients in cases where insufficient amount of tissue was available.

205 Future directions will include detection and longitudinal tracking of ctDNA levels during
206 treatment of early-stage NSCLC. This would include ctDNA detection before and after
207 neoadjuvant therapy, before and after surgery and during follow-up, at regular predetermined time
208 intervals. Also, longitudinal tracking of levels of ctDNA during targeted therapy of metastatic
209 NSCLC will be introduced, in order to detect disease progression before radiologic progression
210 and ensure timely introduction of second-line therapy. A new national guideline for the
211 management of thoracic malignancies is currently being prepared and will include
212 recommendations for liquid biopsy testing into routine clinical practice.

213 **2.2 Cancers of the digestive system**

214 Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) has emerged from an exploratory biomarker to a
215 clinically actionable tool in the management of gastrointestinal (GI) malignancies [5].
216 Management of colorectal cancer, as a highly prevalent cancer but also a high ctDNA-shedding
217 tumor, has in recent years brought important data of clinical utility of ctDNA but also highlighted
218 current difficulties in implementation [5,6], such as variability in ctDNA shedding among tumor
219 types and disease stages, limited sensitivity in very early cancers, lack of standardized assays and
220 thresholds and the need for prospective trials for establishing clinical relevance and impact on

221 survival [5,6]. In GI tract malignancies, detection of ctDNA is used throughout the disease
222 continuum. It offers the possibility to overcome common diagnostic issues, such as limited or
223 unsafe tumor sampling (eg. cholangiocarcinoma and pancreatic carcinoma). It enables
224 comprehensive molecular profiling, facilitating identification of actionable alterations, including
225 HER2 amplification, MSI status, RAS and BRAF mutations and gene fusions, which may guide
226 targeted or immunotherapeutic approaches [5,7–11]. In early-stage disease, ctDNA positivity after
227 curative-intent resection as a marker of measurable residual disease (MRD) is strongly associated
228 with recurrence and inferior survival independent of standard clinicopathologic risk factors [12–
229 14]. These data have established ctDNA as a robust prognostic biomarker in resected stage II–III
230 CRC and have led to ctDNA-guided adjuvant strategies being tested in phase II–III trials, but
231 treatment decisions based solely on ctDNA are not yet adopted in routine practice in early stage
232 [15,16]. In the metastatic setting, ctDNA provides dynamic insight into treatment response and
233 clonal evolution under therapeutic pressure. Serial ctDNA analysis can detect emerging resistance
234 mechanisms, such as *RAS* mutations during anti-EGFR therapy or secondary alterations affecting
235 targeted pathways [17–20].

236 Serbia, as a country with high incidence and mortality from GI malignancies, has
237 substantial need for tools that further enhance patient-centered care [21]. In the future, applying
238 ctDNA as a standard procedure in GI malignancies in Serbia is of paramount importance. First
239 step would be tumor profiling, which is ESMO and NCCN endorsed [22–24]. Next step would be
240 integration of LB across various disease stages: identification and longitudinal follow-up in local
241 stages pre and postoperatively and longitudinal ctDNA real-time monitoring of treatment response
242 and detection of acquired resistance mutations in the metastatic setting.

243 The first Serbian pilot study employing liquid biopsy for determining *RAS/BRAF* mutations
244 in patients with *RAS/BRAF* wild type CRC previously treated with anti-EGFR antibodies, was
245 initiated in 2025. Candidates for EGFR rechallenge strategy in the third line were determined based
246 on previous clinical benefit of first line anti-EGFR therapy, defined as duration of first line
247 treatment of at least 6 months and at least 4 months without active anti-EGFR treatment. By April
248 2026, a total of 81 patients with mCRC were tested using liquid biopsy analysis on the cobas®
249 4800 System (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) after cfDNA extraction with the QIAamp® MinElute®
250 cfDNA Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany). Samples were received from eleven public healthcare
251 institutions and three private clinics across Serbia, reflecting real-world clinical practice. No

252 mutations in the *KRAS*, *NRAS*, or *BRAF* genes were detected in 18 patients (22.2%). A single
253 mutation was identified in 40 patients (49.4%), while 22 patients (27.2%) had two concurrent
254 mutations. Only one patient (1.2%) had more than two detectable mutations in the analyzed genes.
255 The most frequently detected alterations in the *KRAS* gene were located in codon 61. This finding
256 is notable because codon 61 mutations are not commonly observed in initial tissue testing
257 performed before the introduction of anti-EGFR therapy [25]. Detection of these mutations in
258 ctDNA supports previous findings, suggesting that *KRAS* codon 61 alterations play a role in the
259 development of secondary resistance to targeted therapies in patients with metastatic colorectal
260 cancer [26].

261 The number of patients tested in Serbia to date demonstrates an increasing necessity for
262 the integration of liquid biopsy into routine clinical practice for the management of metastatic
263 colorectal cancer. Additionally, these findings highlight the potential advantages of applying more
264 sensitive molecular techniques, such as dPCR or next-generation sequencing (NGS), to enhance
265 mutation detection rates and improve clinical outcomes. A new national guideline for the
266 management of GI malignancies is currently being prepared and will include recommendations for
267 liquid biopsy testing into routine clinical practice.

268 **2.3 Melanoma**

269 Circulating cell-free DNA, particularly circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) carrying
270 melanoma-specific genetic alterations such as mutations in *BRAF*, *NRAS*, *KIT*, and *TERT*, has
271 become a central component of liquid biopsies in melanoma. This enables minimally invasive
272 molecular characterization and longitudinal disease monitoring, overcoming tissue biopsy
273 limitations, including spatial heterogeneity and limited feasibility for repeated sampling [27,28].
274 Increasing evidence highlights ctDNA as a prognostic and predictive biomarker in melanoma.
275 Baseline ctDNA detection is associated with higher tumor burden and poorer outcomes, while on-
276 treatment ctDNA kinetics provide real-time insights into therapeutic efficacy. In patients receiving
277 immune checkpoint inhibitors, early ctDNA clearance strongly correlates with durable responses
278 and improved survival, often anticipating radiologic response, whereas persistent or rising ctDNA
279 levels are linked to early progression and treatment resistance [27,28]. Additionally, ctDNA
280 analysis is significant in molecular residual disease detection. Tumor-informed assays capable of
281 tracking multiple patient-specific variants can identify minimal residual disease following surgery,
282 and predict relapse, months before clinical or imaging confirmation [29], suggesting that ctDNA-

283 guided strategies may enable risk-adapted surveillance and treatment modulation in future clinical
284 workflows. Nevertheless, routine implementation remains limited by reduced sensitivity in
285 patients with low tumor burden, early-stage disease, or isolated central nervous system metastases,
286 and significant variability persists across analytical platforms, pre-analytical procedures, and
287 reporting thresholds. Consequently, assay harmonization and prospective validation are essential
288 to establish standardized clinical use [30]. Furthermore, minimal residual disease monitoring
289 would require better cross validation between national laboratories and international collaboration
290 and licensing procedures.

291 In Serbia, the clinical relevance of ctDNA in melanoma is evaluated through the ReDiMEL
292 project supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, whereby the detection and
293 quantification of ctDNA relies on a tumor-informed approach and usage of the dPCR platform.
294 Preliminary results imply that both the presence and quantity of ctDNA impacts prognosis in ICI-
295 treated patients with advanced melanoma [31]. Furthermore, the results highlight that persistent or
296 rising ctDNA levels reflect treatment resistance and precede clinical progression. ctDNA-based
297 liquid biopsy represents a powerful adjunct to conventional biomarkers, offering tumor-specific
298 information with significant potential to refine personalized melanoma management.

299 **2.4 Hematological malignancies**

300 Hematological malignancies (HMs) are marked by pronounced heterogeneity and dynamic
301 clonal evolution, complicating diagnosis, disease monitoring and treatment, especially in those
302 without typical genetic markers [32]. Involvement of blood associated tissues makes HMs
303 particularly well suited to LB, as tumor-derived components frequently circulate in peripheral
304 blood and other body fluids [33–35]. Current clinical trials are investigating ctDNA for treatment
305 tailoring in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma and primary central nervous system lymphoma, for
306 diagnosis and prognosis in lymphoma, for minimal residual disease detection in acute myeloid
307 leukemia after allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, for early relapse detection in
308 multiple myeloma after autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, miRNA for predicting
309 relapse risk in acute lymphoblastic leukemia, and ctDNA for detecting mutations associated with
310 resistance to targeted therapies in chronic lymphocytic leukemia and chronic myeloid leukemia,
311 etc [33,36–41].

312 Despite its potential, LB-based approaches in HMs are less established and integration into
313 clinical guidelines remains an ongoing challenge [35,42]. What poses a limitation is the marked

314 heterogeneity of HMs, broadly categorized as leukemias, lymphomas, and myelomas, comprising
315 over 100 distinct subtypes [43], which limits sample sizes and complicates robust conclusions. To
316 address this, collaboration and biobank establishment is essential, to standardize methods and
317 enable broad clinical validation [34,38].

318 Classification, diagnosis, and molecular MRD assessment of HMs in Serbia follow international
319 and European guidelines [44,45]. Although not yet focused on LB, translational hemato-oncology
320 research in Serbia is well established and offers substantial resources that could be recruited for
321 this purpose [46–48]. To initiate expert dialogue on integrating LB into hematological clinical
322 practice in Serbia, a dedicated LB in HMs working group should be established between SDIR
323 and the Serbian Society of Hematology to lead this action and develop policy briefs for health
324 policymakers. In HMs, serial monitoring through minimally invasive blood sampling would
325 reduce the need for invasive bone marrow biopsies, enabling early and precise diagnosis, real-time
326 tracking of clonal evolution and resistance mutations, prevention of disease progression into
327 leukemias, MRD assessment and detection of extramedullary disease, fostering desired
328 personalized and adaptive treatment strategies [34,36,38,42,49].

329 Both the EACR and SDIR made substantial effort through various initiatives to
330 demonstrate the potential of LB implementation into clinical practice. In the next step of LB
331 strategy there is an urgent need to encompass HMs in a LB "to-do list", with participation of
332 relevant associations in hematology, where Serbian professionals would make its contribution
333 together with European and world recognized colleagues.

334 **2.5 Oral squamous cell carcinoma**

335 Oral cancer consistently ranks among the ten most frequently diagnosed malignancies
336 worldwide. It is an aggressive disease, marked by a high risk of recurrence and metastasis.
337 Moreover, invasive surgical interventions often result in severe functional and aesthetic sequelae,
338 leading to a markedly reduced quality of life. The vast majority of oral cancers are strongly
339 associated with tobacco and alcohol use and are histologically classified as oral squamous cell
340 carcinomas (OSCC). Despite substantial advances in medical research and therapeutic strategies,
341 overall survival rates have shown only minimal improvement over recent decades. Serbia occupies
342 a middle-to-higher position among European countries with respect to oral cancer incidence and
343 mortality, the latter remaining relatively elevated due to late-stage diagnosis [50].

344 Traditional staging systems for head and neck cancers, including TNM classification, remain
345 largely dependent on clinical and radiological parameters, which fail to capture the molecular
346 complexity of OSCC. Additional histopathological features such as perineural invasion,
347 lymphovascular invasion, and depth of invasion provide prognostic value but remain insufficient
348 for precise risk stratification.

349 Although molecular heterogeneity is a defining feature of OSCC, several genes are consistently
350 altered, structurally or functionally, such as TP53, CDKN2A, PIK3CA, HRAS, NOTCH1, etc. as
351 demonstrated by large-scale genomic studies [51,52]. These recurrent mutations have provided
352 key insights into the molecular pathogenesis of the disease but despite these advances, the
353 translation of genomic findings into routine clinical practice remains limited. This gap is largely
354 due to the scarcity of adequate biopsy material, intratumoral heterogeneity, and the challenges
355 associated with integrating complex molecular data into established diagnostic and therapeutic
356 frameworks [53].

357 In this context, liquid biopsy (LB) has emerged as a promising complementary approach.
358 Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) analysis enables non-invasive, real-time monitoring of tumor
359 dynamics, including tumor burden, treatment response, and early detection of recurrence [54]. In
360 OSCC specifically, saliva represents a particularly advantageous biofluid due to its proximity to
361 the tumor site, ease of collection, and high patient acceptability. Studies have demonstrated that
362 tumor-specific mutations can be reliably detected in salivary ctDNA, and demonstrated the
363 underlying potential in early detection and relapse prediction [55,56]. A novel approach is the
364 analysis of exosomes in OSCCB. These small extracellular vesicles carry LB-derived nucleic acids
365 (DNA, RNA, and microRNAs), proteins, and lipids that reflect the molecular state of the parent
366 tumor cells and their contents might provide a “snapshot” of tumor biology [57]. Although their
367 clinical implementation remains limited by technical challenges related to their isolation,
368 characterization, and standardization, emerging evidence shows their strong potential as
369 diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic biomarkers in cancer, including OSCC [58].

370 Ultimately, incorporating such molecular insights into standard care pathways would represent
371 a critical step toward the implementation of personalized medicine in OSCC. Outside the scope of
372 research projects, LB has not been implemented in the clinical management of OSCC in Serbia so
373 far. First clinical needs would be to enhance the OSCC diagnostic accuracy, and improve patient
374 outcomes after treatment, reshaping the allocation of healthcare resources.

375 **3. Companion diagnostics and technological advances**

376 A companion diagnostic (CDx) test gives information that is crucial for the optimal use of
377 a—corresponding therapy. As demand for biomarker-based CDx tests in modern oncology
378 increases, implementing adequate Quality control (QC) to ensure the accuracy, reproducibility, and
379 reliability of molecular diagnostic tests, is of the utmost importance.

380 A schematical representation of tissue-based and liquid-biopsy based companion
381 diagnostics methods centrally employed at the IORS Laboratory of Molecular Genetics in the
382 period 2008-2026 is presented in Fig3.

383 **Figure 3.** Schematical representation of tissue-based and liquid-biopsy based companion
384 diagnostics methods centrally employed at IORS in the period 2008-2026.
385
386

387 Shortly after the implementation of the cobas *EGFR* Mutation Test v2 at IORS (the first
388 FDA-approved, blood-based companion diagnostic that can detect *EGFR* gene mutations in
389 NSCLC patients [59]), Laboratory for Molecular genetics of IORS took part in quality assurance
390 (QA) schemes, organized by the leading global provider of quality assurance tools, European
391 Molecular Genetics Quality Network (EMQN⁷). EMQN integrates a composite approach to

⁷ <https://www.emqn.org/>

392 address pre-analytic, analytic, and post analytic (interpretation) steps. Acknowledging the
393 importance of standardized pre-analytic processes in molecular testing in liquid biopsy, in 2024,
394 EMQN organized a pilot scheme for cfDNA isolation from plasma. Also, through the work of its
395 Quality Control and Accreditation Committee, the International Society of Liquid Biopsy (ISLB)
396 has brought together an international panel of experts, including EMQN, to present the first global
397 framework for quality assurance in liquid biopsy [60]. Molecular diagnostics is rapidly evolving,
398 fostering ingenuity and adopting technological advances. Robotic systems can simplify molecular
399 testing, reduce human error, and provide timely monitoring of test performance. It will be required
400 of QA to continually adapt in order to address these new technical challenges. The rapid
401 development of bioinformatics tools contributes to faster and more accurate data analysis and
402 variant calling. It is imperative for every laboratory engaged in molecular testing to keep up with
403 technological innovations and, where possible, implement them into routine practice, along with
404 continuous participation in QA schemes.

405 Optimizing preanalytical and analytical methods for cfDNA processing is crucial to enable
406 sensitive and specific detection of biomarkers, especially in clinical settings where ctDNA fraction
407 is scarce, such as for early cancer detection and minimal residual disease monitoring [61]. A typical
408 10mL blood draw yield approximately 3000 genome equivalents (GE) corresponding to ~10ng of
409 cfDNA, and the tumor derived ctDNA often represents a minority fraction (0.01% - 10%) of the
410 total [62]. While there are many commercial methods for cfDNA extraction, starting volumes,
411 cfDNA yield and concentration should be determined for each application.

412 The choice of analytical method will depend on the number of required biomarkers. For a
413 small number of targets digital (droplet) PCR platforms (e.g. BioRad's ddPCR and RainDance,
414 Applied Biosystems' AbsoluteQ) offer the highest sensitivity (down to 0.001%). However, the
415 sample concentration should be titrated carefully, as most platforms have a range between 0 to
416 20000 GE, and limited target multiplexing. Quantitative PCR has the advantage of higher target-
417 multiplexing albeit with a higher limit of detection (LoD) compared to dPCR.

418 NGS allows for a simultaneous detection of anywhere between tens of thousands of
419 variants and whole genome analysis in a single assay. However, the assay sensitivity depends
420 greatly on the choice of the library preparation method for NGS. Library preparation methods
421 based on adapter ligation suffer from low efficiency and procedural loss. Furthermore, the
422 efficiency of target enrichment by hybridization capture increases with the size of the panel, being

423 optimal for large panels (>100MB). Target specific PCR-based enrichment methods (e.g. Tam-Seq
424 [63]), Duplex-seq [64] are better suited for smaller panels, with superior analytical specificity
425 compared to hybridization capture, but may be hampered by short cfDNA lacking anchoring site
426 for both forward and reverse primers thus reducing analytical sensitivity. This hurdle was
427 surpassed by single-primer chemistry entailing one target-specific and one universal primer
428 offered by several providers (e.g. QIAGEN QiaSeq Targeted, NuGEN SPET (United States Patent
429 9,650,628)) or in-house protocols⁸.

430 Epimutations, in the form of aberrant DNA methylation marks, have gained prominence as
431 attractive cfDNA biomarkers, yet their analysis presents additional challenges. Whole-genome
432 bisulfite sequencing (WGBS-seq) is regarded as the gold standard for DNA methylation analysis
433 due to its digital readout and single-base resolution; however, it is hindered by DNA degradation,
434 which results in diminished sequencing complexity, lower mapping rates, and escalating
435 sequencing costs. Recently, several new technologies emerged to enable bisulfite-free conversion
436 of unmethylated cytosines to uracils using TET-APOBEC enzymes (NEB EM-seq, Visium)
437 avoiding DNA degradation, or to directly convert only methylated cytosines to uracils allowing in
438 addition for increased mapping rates and simultaneous detection of genetic and epigenetic variants.
439 This can be achieved using TET enzyme combined with pyridine borane chemistry (TAPS) [65],
440 recently improved and commercialized as TAPS+ by Watchmaker Genomics or using proprietary
441 chemistry for 5-base sequencing launched in 2026 by Illumina. Additionally, ‘biomodal’
442 commercialized an enzyme-based library prep method for 6-base genome reading to enable
443 simultaneous sequencing of genetic and epigenetic (5mC and 5hmC) variants in cfDNA [66]. This
444 multi-analyte detection may enhance the precision of cfDNA biomarkers paving the way for a
445 wider adoption in precision oncology.

446 In the future, national efforts will need to incorporate these new and emerging technologies
447 into routine clinical practice, evaluating best practices and infrastructural and financial resources.

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⁸ <https://doi-org.libproxy.ucl.ac.uk/10.1186/s12864-016-3425-4>

452 **4. Scientific projects**

453 Pilot clinical programs and scientific projects in several avenues of translational research using
454 liquid biopsies have been ongoing since 2016. The TRACEPIGEN⁹ project funded by the national
455 Science Fund of Serbia included a longitudinal prospective study collecting samples of patients
456 with advanced lung and colorectal cancer during systemic therapy with a focus on genetic and
457 epigenetic evolution aspects. Within the framework of the Horizon Europe project
458 STEPUPIORS¹⁰, a first organized liquid biopsy rectal cancer biobank was established for future
459 scientific collaborative efforts, enabling the evaluation of LB significance in treatment response
460 and MRD. Evaluation of the clinical relevance of ctDNA in melanoma is ongoing through the
461 ReDiMEL¹¹ project supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia and first results were
462 presented at the SDIR Regional congress in Belgrade in 2025. The EXPAND-EV¹² Horizon
463 Europe project and the RESCALE-EV¹³ project supported of the Science Fund of the Republic of
464 Serbia are focused on exploring the potential of extracellular vesicles from plasma and pleural
465 effusion LB sources in precision medicine.

466 **5. Educational efforts**

467 The Serbian Society for Medical Oncology (UMOS) and the Serbian Association for Cancer
468 Research (SDIR) are well positioned to collaboratively lead a nationwide liquid biopsy (LB)
469 education initiative, rooted within established clinical pathways. Such a tiered educational
470 framework will be aligned with international evidence-based guidelines, notably the ESMO
471 recommendations, ensuring harmonization with global standards [22]. Recent national and
472 international initiatives, such as the UMOS–SDIR Liquid Biopsy Working Group and the
473 STEPUPIORS project highlight both the existing capacity and the growing professional
474 commitment in this field¹⁴. Nevertheless, the adoption of liquid biopsy remains uneven across
475 institutions, underscoring the need for broader standardization and integration.

476 Next educational efforts must cover clinical indications for LB, pre-analytical variables
477 influencing assay reliability, and the principles of assay selection across platforms such as PCR,

⁹ <https://www.tracepigen.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.stepupiors.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/redimel-project/>

¹² <https://www.expand-ev.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.rescale-ev.rs/en/>

¹⁴ <https://english.sdir.ac.rs/first-umos-sdir-colloquium-liquid-biopsy-in-oncology-today/>

478 digital PCR, and NGS. Emphasis should be placed on analytical sensitivity, specificity, and
479 reproducibility, providing learners with a robust understanding of methodological rigor. At the
480 practical level, structured courses should address sample collection and management, standardized
481 reporting protocols, and integration of LB results into clinical decision-making algorithms, along
482 with real-world applications in oncology practice. At the continuous education level, national
483 meetings, workshops, and e-learning platforms should ensure sustained professional development.
484 The curriculum should be tailored to diverse professional groups - laboratory medicine specialists,
485 pathologists, molecular biologists, and oncologists - while remaining consistent with international
486 recommendations (ESMO, American Society of Clinical Oncology/College of American
487 Pathologists (ASCO/CAP)). Finally, integration into International Organization for
488 Standardization ISO 15189 quality management systems will guarantee that LB education is not
489 only scientifically rigorous but also embedded within accredited laboratory practices [67]. This
490 multi-tiered approach ensures that Serbia's LB education initiative is comprehensive,
491 internationally benchmarked, and capable of advancing both clinical practice and research
492 innovation.

493 The next educational event in joint organization of UMOS and SDIR is planned for Autumn
494 2026, covering basic topics of molecular oncology for clinicians, as well as a brief overview of
495 usability of LB in the clinic. Future educational events aim to include a wider medical and research
496 audience in collaboration with national societies of oncological surgeons, pathologists, geneticists
497 and biochemists.

498 SDIR has also launched a national oncological journal Oncology Insights in 2023, with the
499 aim to use this electronic and hard copy platform for scientific education and presentation of
500 ongoing studies. In the first 3 volumes, various LB aspects have been prominently elaborated in
501 both research and review articles [68–70].

502 **6. 2026-2030 Roadmap and Joint UMOS-SDIR Policy Recommendation Statement**

503 At the moment, LB testing is used in LC at progression on EGFR TKIs and at diagnosis, if
504 tissue biopsy is not available. In CRC, LB testing is not routinely used in the clinic. Expansion of
505 national indications in the first step should include approaches presented in Table 1.

506

507 **Table 1. UMOS-SDIR Liquid biopsy implementation national recommendations for the**
 508 **period 2026-2030.**

Cancer type	Cancer stage	Implementation setting	OCEBM LoE*
Lung cancer	I-III A	ctDNA detection	3
	III B-IV	ctDNA monitoring during treatment	3
Colorectal cancer	II-III	ctDNA monitoring during treatment and/or follow up	4
	IV	ctDNA monitoring during treatment	3

509 *OCEBM LoE - Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine Levels of Evidence

510 Prior to next steps, detailed health technology assessment analyses will need to be performed
 511 for each planned implementation setting. Also, prospective observational trials in the setting of
 512 Serbian hospitals will be needed to obtain real-world feasibility data. A pilot study in the CRC
 513 setting showed that a prospective observational trial integrating ctDNA in clinical follow up would
 514 not add more than 10% of total treatment cost¹⁵.

515 Members of the UMOS-SDIR intersociety working group for LB will liaise between clinicians,
 516 researchers, the business sector, national policy makers and relevant governmental institutions to
 517 construct a clear national strategy and implementation plan for technological and resource
 518 advancement using a cost-sustainable approach in the period 2026-2030. The first prospective
 519 observational study integrating prospective LB sampling into the standard follow up of patients
 520 with CRC is expected to be launched in 2027.

521

522 **Data accessibility**

523 No data was generated within the study.

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 530 33/2026-03/200015; 451-03-34/2026-03/ 200110).

¹⁵ https://www.stepupiors.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/Milena-Cavic_MSc-Thesis.pdf

531 **Author Contributions**

532 MC, JS, DR, RJ - Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology,
533 Visualization, Funding acquisition, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing-original draft,
534 Writing-review and editing. NN, AD, VS, VC, BCA, MT, DM, AB, DT, SVP, IM, FDj, MM, ADj
535 - Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing-original draft, Writing-
536 review and editing. JM, LK, ZC, NM - Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation,
537 Methodology, Funding acquisition, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing-original draft,
538 Writing-review and editing. BZ, BK, MR, MMK - Investigation, Methodology, Writing-review
539 and editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

540 **Conflict of interest**

541 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

542 **Ethics approval**

543 Results of diagnostics analyses were derived from regular clinical workflow with patients' consent
544 and were approved by the Ethics committees of the corresponding hospitals. No patient data was
545 used for the preparation of this manuscript.

546 **Use of generative AI**

547 During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT by OpenAI only for language
548 editing and stylistic improvement. After using this tool, the author(s) carefully reviewed and edited
549 the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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